

Dielectric behaviour of *n*-decanol ethanolamine mixtures at microwave frequencies

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Abstract : Values of dielectric constant (ϵ') and loss factor (ϵ'') have been experimentally determined for binary liquid mixtures of *n*-decanol + ethanolamine at 6.7 GHz microwave frequencies at 39 °C. The values of ϵ' and ϵ'' have been used to evaluate the molar polarization, apparent polarization and the excess activation energy, viscosity and viscous flow have also been calculated. These parameters have been used to explain the formation of 2 : 1 complexes for the system (*n*-decanol + ethanolamine).

Keywords : Dielectric behaviour, polarization, *n*-decanol, ethanolamine, excess parameters, binary mixtures.

Introduction

When a binary mixture is formed, the viscosity and dielectric parameters do not vary linearly. The deviation from linearity of these parameters is termed as excess parameters and is helpful to understand the nature of bonding between the two liquids. Recently several workers¹⁻⁵ have studied the excess parameters in liquid mixtures.

The nature of complex formation between the molecules may be ascertained by studying apparent molar polarization and is useful in determining the nature of molecular interactions in the liquid systems.

Singh and Sharma have studied the dielectric parameters of ketone-amine binary mixtures and Narwade and Gawali³ have studied the *n*-propyl alcohol-ethylenediamine binary mixtures. Dielectric studies of *n*-decanol + ethanolamine mixtures have not been carried out in the past.

As such it was felt that the present studies may provide useful information of complexes in the mixtures of *n*-decanol + ethanolamine.

Experimental

The dielectric constant (ϵ') and the loss factor (ϵ'') were measured using Surber's¹⁰ technique of measuring the reflection co-efficient from the air-dielectric boundary of the liquid in the microwave *J*-band at 6.7 GHz frequency at 39 °C temperature.

The power loss in dielectric may be expressed as a function of dissipation factor D , defined by

$$D = \frac{\epsilon''}{\epsilon' - \left(\frac{\lambda_0}{\lambda_c}\right)^2}$$
$$D = \frac{\tan \delta}{1 - \left(\frac{1}{\epsilon'}\right)\left(\frac{\lambda_0}{\lambda_c}\right)^2} \quad (1)$$

where, λ_0 is the free space wavelength and λ_c is the cut-off wavelength for the wave guide.

The propagation constant for the dielectric filled guide may be written as

$$\gamma_d = \alpha_d + j \left(\frac{2\pi}{\lambda_d}\right) \quad (2)$$

where α_d is the attenuation constant due to dielectric and λ_d is the wavelength of the electromagnetic wave in the waveguide filled with the dielectric. Surber has derived the following relations for the dielectric parameters D , ϵ' and ϵ'' .

$$D = \tan \left[2 \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{\alpha_d \lambda_d}{2\pi} \right) \right] \quad (3)$$

$$\epsilon' = \left(\frac{\lambda_0}{\lambda_c}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\lambda_0}{\lambda_d}\right)^2 \left[1 - \tan^2 \left(\frac{1}{2} \tan^{-1} D \right) \right] \quad (4)$$

where, $\alpha_d \lambda_d$ is the attenuation per wavelength. Now the parameters to be measured experimentally are λ_d and $\alpha_d \lambda_d$.

In order to determine the above quantities, the movable short of the liquid cell was moved in and out. The corresponding reflection co-efficient⁷ was measured by means of the crystal pick-up in the directional coupler. The relationship between the reflected power and the depth of the liquid column is approximately given by a damped sinusoidal wave. The distance between two adjacent minimas of this curve gives dielectric wavelength (λ_d).

The dissipation factor D for the system may be computed analytically as follows.

$$M_n = \frac{|\Gamma_n^2|^2}{|\Gamma_\infty^2|^2} = \frac{I_n}{I_\infty} \quad (6)$$

where, $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots$, $|\Gamma_n|$ is the reflection co-efficient by the liquid column of length $L = n \left(\frac{\lambda_d}{2} \right)$ and $|\Gamma_\infty|$ is the reflection co-efficient for the liquid column of infinite length. I_n and I_∞ represent corresponding current values.

Let

$$x = \frac{\lambda_d}{\lambda_g} \quad (7)$$

$$y = \frac{(1-x)}{(1+x)} \quad (8)$$

According to Surber, attenuation per wavelength is given by

$$\alpha_d \lambda_d = \frac{1}{n} \log k_1 \{1 + (1 + k_2)^{1/2}\} \quad (9)$$

where,

$$K_1 = \frac{1 - M_n Y^2}{Y (M_n - 1)} \quad (10)$$

and

$$K_2 = \frac{(M_n - 1) (1 - M_n Y^4)}{(1 - M_n Y^2)^2} \quad (11)$$

The values of parameters D , ϵ' and ϵ'' may be calculated by using above equation.

The density and viscosity of the pure components and their mixtures were measured by using the density bottle and Ostwald's viscometer respectively.

Ethanolamine (AR grade) supplied by Merck-Mumbai, India was used as such, while n -decanol (AR grade) supplied by S.d. Fine, Mumbai, India were used.

The two liquids according to their properties were mixed well and kept for 4 to 5 h in a well stoppered bottle to ensure good thermal equilibrium.

Results and discussion

The values of viscosity (η), dielectric constant (ϵ'), loss factor (ϵ''), loss tangent ($\tan \delta$) and activation energy (E_a) for the viscous flow, with increasing mole fraction (x) of ethanolamine for the binary mixture of ethanolamine + n -decanol are listed in Table 1.

The variation of the dielectric constant (ϵ') with molar concentration of ethanolamine in the mixture is presented in Fig. 2. In this case the curve shows deviation from linearity, indicating complex formation in the mixture as suggested by Job. The deviation is occurred at 0.5225,

Table 1. Values of mole fraction (X) of ethanolamine, density (ρ), viscosity (η), dielectric constant (ϵ'), loss factor (ϵ''), loss tangent ($\tan \delta$), activation energy (E_a) and molar polarization (P_{12}) for the binary liquid system of ethanolamine + n -decanol at 39 °C

X	ρ	η (CP)	ϵ'	ϵ''	$\tan \delta$	E_a (kcal/mol)	P_{12}
0.0000	0.80	5.563	2.31111	0.17135	0.7414	7.00706	6.6170
0.3117	0.825	7.020	3.3191	1.1004	0.3315	7.1510	6.7638
0.5225	0.839	8.039	4.04113	0.1788	0.0442	7.2348	6.5320
0.6554	0.86	8.477	4.4653	1.2190	0.2729	7.2676	5.8165
0.7602	0.88	9.596	5.3649	1.09834	0.2047	7.3442	5.6833
0.8402	0.91	10.342	5.5880	2.8145	0.5110	7.3906	5.0065
0.9049	0.943	10.283	6.8084	3.8793	0.5698	7.3870	4.9178
0.9569	0.973	9.534	7.8109	5.3852	0.6895	7.3402	4.6663
1.0000	0.995	9.462	13.1512	2.1849	0.1661	7.3316	4.9661

Fig. 1. Variation of dielectric constant vs mole fraction of ethanolamine.

Fig. 2. Variation of loss tangent vs mole fraction of ethanolamine.

0.7602 and 0.9569 mole fraction of ethanolamine. But the maximum deviation is formed at 0.9569 mole fraction of ethanolamine.

Hence greatest chances of complex formation is at $x = 0.9569$.

It is seen from Fig. 2, that the absorption in the mixture is minimum than that of pure liquid state. It is clear from curve that the loss is minimum or at $x = 0.5225$ mole fraction of ethanolamine. The environment and temperature being identical throughout the relative proportions of the interacting species should have bearing on the large absorption of energy. An interaction causing association between two types of molecules may be responsible for non linear behaviour.

The viscosity curve indicates that, the solute-solute interaction between ethanolamine and *n*-decanol increased to a maximum value around at 0.84 mole fraction of

ethanolamine. Therefore, it seems reasonable to assume that, the formation of associates range is held together by comparatively stronger intermolecular dipole-dipole interactions.

Fig. 3. Variation of viscosity vs mole fraction of ethanolamine.

Molar and apparent polarization :

The values of polarization of the mixtures were obtained using the formula.

$$P_{12} = \frac{\epsilon' - 1}{\epsilon' + 2} \times \frac{X_1M_1 + X_2M_2}{d} \tag{12}$$

where, M_1 and M_2 are the molecular weights, X_1 and X_2 the molar concentrations of the constituents of the mixture and d the density of the mixture.

Then following Earp and Glasstone¹¹ and assuming the formula

$$P_{12} = X_1P_1 + X_2P_2 \tag{13}$$

where, P_2 is the apparent polarization of each liquid in the mixture, if P_1 is the polarization of the other component of the mixture in the pure liquid state.

Values of P_1 and P_2 were calculated. The values of molar polarization P_{12} are plotted in Fig. 4, as a function of ethanolamine in the mixture.

We may interpret Fig. 4 as representing two regions (high and low ethanolamine concentrations), the intersection of the straight lines representing these separate regions can interpreted as ideally representing the point of maximum concentration of complex. The point of intersection for both the systems occurs at about 0.76 which corresponds to a 2 : 1 complex for the system.

Fig. 4. Variation of molar polarization vs mole fraction of ethanolamine.

Fig. 5. Variation of P_2 vs mole fraction of ethanolamine.

Table 2. Values of excess parameters $\Delta\epsilon'$, $\Delta\epsilon''$, $\Delta\eta$, ΔE_a and P_2 along with mole fraction (X) of ethanolamine for the binary liquid system of ethanolamine + *n*-decanol

X	$\Delta\epsilon'$	$\Delta\epsilon''$	$\Delta\eta$	ΔE_a	P_2
0.0000					
0.3117	-6.3730	-0.9375	0.2605	0.0431	7.5769
0.5225	-3.5602	-1.778	0.4219	0.026	8.0946
0.6554	-1.5318	-0.6488	0.8599	0.0742	7.5886
0.7602	-0.4546	-0.7283	0.1114	0.0904	7.9461
0.8402	1.4719	1.0260	1.551	0.1110	5.2017
0.9049	3.4660	2.1210	1.2462	0.0864	4.4251
0.9569	5.0329	3.6514	0.2976	0.02269	-2.060
1.0000					

Fig. 6. Variation of $\Delta\eta$ vs mole fraction of ethanolamine.

The values of the apparent polarization for *n*-decanol as a function of mole fraction of ethanolamine in Fig. 5. The flat portion of this curve clearly indicates that the formation of complex in the ethanolamine + *n*-decanol mixtures. The more pronounced the flat portion, the more stable is the complex.

Excess parameters :

The excess values of viscosity $\Delta\eta$, excess activation energy ΔE_a for binary mixture ethanolamine + *n*-decanol are represented in Figs. 6 and 7. The excess values were then calculated by using relations of the form,

$$\Delta Y = Y_m - (X_1 Y_1 + X_2 Y_2) \quad (14)$$

where, ΔY is any excess parameter and Y refers to the mentioned quantities. The subscripts m , 1 and 2 used in the above equation are respectively for the mixture, component 1 and 2, X_1 and X_2 are the mole fractions of the components in the liquid mixtures.

Fig. 7. Variation of activation energy vs mole fraction of ethanolamine.

The excess viscosity, activation energy are all positive, indicating strong interactions between ethanolamine and *n*-decanol molecules. For all these excess parameters the maxima for the ethanolamine + *n*-decanol mixture occurs at about 0.8 fraction of ethanolamine.

The deviation of excess activation energy indicates the increase in the internal energy of the viscous flow.

Conclusion :

(i) The dielectric constant, dielectric loss, loss tangent, molar polarization and excess dielectric parameters are reported for binary mixture of *n*-decanol + ethanolamine.

(ii) Non-linear behaviour of dielectric constant versus mole fraction of ethanolamine indicates the formation of complex in the mixture.

(iii) $\tan \delta$ curve indicates that microwave energy is minimum in the mixture than that of pure liquids.

(iv) The molar polarization curve suggests the 2 : 1 type complex formation in the binary mixture.

(v) Deviation of excess parameters from linearity suggests solute-solute interaction in the mixture.

References

1. J. K. Das and B. B. Swain, *Indian J. Pure Appl. Phys.*, 1995, **33**, 45.
2. K. Govindan and G. Ravichandran, *Indian J. Pure Appl. Phys.*, 1994, **32**, 852.
3. B. S. Narwade, P. G. Gawali and G. M. Kalmse, *J. Chem., Sci., Part-6*, 2005, 117.
4. P. J. Singh and K. S. Sharma, *Pramana J. Phys.*, 1996, **46**, 4.
5. A. C. Kumbharkhane, S. N. Helambe, S. Doraiswami and S. C. Mehrotra, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1993, **99**, 2405.
6. C. P. Smyth, "Dielectric Behaviour and Structure", McGraw Hill Book Co. Inc., New York, 1955.
7. R. H. Fattepur, M. T. Hosmani, D. K. Deshpande, R. L. Patil and S. C. Mehrotra, *Pramana J. Phys.*, 1995, **44**, 33.
8. P. G. Gawali, B. S. Narwade, Rekha Pande and G. M. Kalmse, "Ferroelectrics and Dielectrics", Allied Pub., Delhi, 2004, 294.
9. P. J. Singh and K. S. Sharma, *Indian J. Pure Appl. Phys.*, 1993, **31**, 721.
10. W. H. Surber, *J. Appl. Phys.*, 1948, **19**, 514.
11. D. P. Earp and S. Glastone, *J. Chem. Soc., Part-11*, 1935, 1709.

